

A Study of Stock Market Awareness and Participation Among College Students.

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Abstract:

Stock market is known as a pulse of economy which reflects the economic conditions of a country. Investors play the major role in the stock market. Their education and awareness, hold the key to reviving and sustaining their interests in the securities market. Stock market awareness comes under the wider concept of financial literacy. This study is an attempt to assess the awareness of youth about various aspects of stock market including concepts, products, processes, institutions etc. The results of the study reveal that the sample youth possess low to medium level of stock market knowledge, and the awareness level is not significantly different among different sample groups based on the discipline they are studying. Young generation these days are more creative and techno-savvy than the older generation socially and financially. One question may arise on whether this generation is concerned about and aware of their financial status in the future and investment. Behavioural Finance is an emerging field that combines the understanding of behavioural and cognitive psychology with financial decision-making process. The traditional economic theory tells us about efficient markets and people making rational decisions to maximize profits. However, the emerging changes tell us that market is not efficient, especially in the short run, and people do not make rational decisions to maximize profits. This research seeks to find the awareness towards investment among young generation. This study used primary data by questionnaire. The objective of this is to find out the relationship awareness and the fore-mentioned independent variables. The study tells us whether the youth are aware about the stock market what is their perspective etc. The result reveals that the key driven on investment among young generation is mainly based on independent variables selected. Finally, the limitations and recommendations are included to help further researchers to have a better finding of the result.

Introduction:

The Stock Market is the very vast, complex network of trading activities where shares of the companies are bought and sold, which are protected by laws against fraud and other unfair trading practices. The stock market is also known as the pulse of the economy, as it reflects the economic condition of a country where investors are the backbone of the stock market. The stock market is a vast, complex network of trading activities where shares of companies are bought and sold, protected by laws against fraud and other unfair trading practices. It

plays a crucial role in modern economies by enabling money to move between investors and companies. Sometimes the best way to see how something works is to look at its parts. In that light, let's review the major elements of the stock market, from the companies' selling shares to stocks to exchanges to the indexes that give us a picture of the stock market's health.

About Stock Market:

Stock markets are fascinating entities and not for the least because they help investors make money. The Securities Contracts (Regulation) Act

of 1956 defines a stock exchange as “anybody of individuals, whether incorporated or not, constituted before corporatization demutualization” or “a body corporate incorporated under the Companies Act, 1956 whether under a scheme of corporatization and demutualization or otherwise,” for the purpose of assisting, regulating or controlling the business of buying, selling or dealing in securities.

Investing is very much essential these days as savings alone is not sufficient to fulfil all our financial goals and to beat inflation. There are several investment options available, and you can choose them as per your needs and convenience. You must start your investments right from a young age to get good returns. Investment habit brings a sense of financial discipline in a person’s life as it makes you allocate a certain amount of money periodically for the purpose of investment. Based on your risk appetite and time horizon to achieve your financial goals, you can select the appropriate investment option. Trading can be done in a easily and in less time. Before the advent of online technologies, trading was a complex process as you had to visit the broker or call your broker for placing or cancelling trade orders. Now, you can carry out trading even through a smartphone in the simplest way. rapid increase of social media platforms has reshaped the landscape of financial decision-making, particularly among young investors. Online communities, investment forums, and influencer-driven narratives on platforms such as Twitter, Reddit, and YouTube have created a dynamic environment where information spreads at unprecedented speed. This study investigates are the young youth aware about the modern stock market practices or not. By combining quantitative survey data with qualitative sentiment analysis of social media content, the research explores the extent to which digital

interactions amplify emotional responses and affect trading patterns.

Review of Literature:

Worrell, D. L., Davidson, W. N., & Glascock, J. L. (1993)._: The study investigates about investors' reactions to announcements. We found announcements containing information about permanent replacements to the associated with positive market reactions, whereas other types of firing announcements resulted in no market response. In addition, outsider appointments were perceived as beneficial immediately, while insider appointments elicited a wait-and-see reaction.

A Manorselvi & Ulchi (2019): Researcher has explained the need for efficiency in the stock market to provide students with sufficient knowledge before investing money in the stock market. Students understand market volatility and invest in the best investment propositions. Moreover, after thorough analysis, the path to return on investment is paved.

Objective of the Study:

- 1) To know the awareness among students regarding the stock market.
- 2) To assess the students trading and investing habits.
- 3) To identify and analyse the consequences of these trading habits.

Research methodology:

The present study follows a descriptive research design. It is quantitative in nature as it collects numerical data through structured questionnaire and analyse the responses through statistical tools.

Sources of Data:

This study's goals were achieved using the descriptive research technique as its

methodology. We went out to students and had them fill out questionnaires as primary sources, which provided the information needed to accomplish the study's goals and secondary data. Main purpose of questionnaire is to collect data from those who fill it out. Questions about stock market knowledge and involvement are included in the questionnaire. There are multiple choice and closed ended questions on the survey.

Population and Sample Size: Our sample size is of 100 students. There is a good representation of both undergraduate and graduate students in this sample.

Data Collection: Primary Data: To get the main data, we used a survey strategy including questionnaires and to gather information from respondents online. secondary data: It was used to compliment primary data, which was collected through various textbooks, journals, and research articles. Various statistical tools were used after coding and inputting surveyed data.

Hypothesis for the Study:

H0: There is no awareness on stock market among college students.

H1: There is awareness on stock market among college students.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Interpretation: The above data states that 83% fall in age group between 18-22 where 13% falls in 22-26 and 4% falls in age 26-30.

What comes to your Mind when you consider investing in stock market?

Interpretation: The above data states that 11% student's mindset is very positive whereas 11% are normally positive and 36% students are neutral. Only 11% students are having negative mindset about investing in stock market.

Are you a Demat Account Holder?

Interpretation: The above data states that only 32% students are having demat account whereas 68% students are not having demat account.

Is your college providing any educational programmes related to stock market?

Interpretation: By doing the survey we come to know 63% respondents' states that their colleges are not providing any educational programs related to stock market. Only 37% respondent's states that their college is providing the required educational programs.

What do you see when it comes to investing in stocks?

Interpretation: The above data states that 78% respondents see opportunities in stock market whereas 22% sees risk in it.

Key Findings:

Majority of the respondents 66% are male and 34% are female.

- All the respondents are well educated.
- Majority of respondents are Freshers in Share Market.
- Majority of respondents are aware of the regulator of Capital Market in India.
- Maximum investors are aware of all the investment options.
- Investors do not invest in a single avenue. They prefer different avenues and maximum respondents prefer to invest in shares, mutual funds & bonds.
- The investment plan of majority of respondents is long term, they prefer delivery trading in Share Market.
- All the respondents are aware of all the Online trading apps and according to maximum respondents Upstox and Zerodha are the best online trading app.
- Majority of respondents have positive and neutral perception about stock market and investing and hence majority of the respondents take stock market and investing as an opportunity.
- Majority of respondents think that Stock market and investing is better option in

future to create maximum wealth.

Suggestions:

1. People at young age should be encouraged to invest in the stock market.
2. Initial margin money is high. That money should be low.
3. Try to avoid blindly following the crowd, invest in what you understand.
4. One should have discipline and must follow your plans/ strategies.
5. Start with small amount and try to gain maximum knowledge by practically doing it and avoid investing in free tips and advice.

Conclusion:

After conducting research on the topic 'Awareness and participation in the stock market among students' we come to know that there has been a huge shift in the awareness and participation in the stock market. However, due to the risk involved in the financial markets, several respondents showed someone-participation. Also, the respondents who had partial knowledge of the subject were also not participating in the stock market due to the market risk involved. The students are aware about the basics of share market, but not that much of knowledge about facilities in share market. So, awareness should be spread through advertisement medias like newspaper, television, and magazines, etc. General awareness regarding BSE and NSE should be spread through college syllabus and activities. Also, awareness about Intraday trading and the facilities provided by different stock broking companies should be created through proper guidelines and mediums. Hence the awareness of the stock market was important to the investors because of without knowing any information; it leads to heavy loss and its never adjusting the forthcoming investment also.

Participating in the stock market can provide long-term benefits such as wealth creation and financial security, it is critical for undergraduate students to be aware of and knowledgeable about investing in the stockmarket.

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